

MAHMUDJON TADJIBOEV-MASTER OF MAQAM ART

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Abstract: This article highlights the life and artistic activity of the Uzbek maqam performer and master of maqam art, Mahmudjon Tadjiboev. In particular, it examines the unique aspects of his school of students and his contributions to the development and preservation of maqam art, presented from a scholarly perspective.

Keywords: Mahmudjon Tadjiboev, maqam, art, teacher-student, school, traditional singing.

The Fergana Valley has been full of sensitive poets, artists, craftsmen, and wonderful musicians and hafiz since time immemorial. I don't think it is necessary to list the names of master artists who passed away in the recent past. Because almost all art masters, from teachers Hamrokul Qori to Zhorakhan Sultanov or from Ma'murjon Uzokov to Fattahkhan Mamadaliyev, people who do not pay attention to art know these artists very well, that the Fergana Valley is a land of unique hafiz and great musicians. In this area, it is clear to everyone that the cities of Kokan, Margilon, Andijan, Namangan have been formed as economic and social centers in the Fergana Valley since ancient times. In addition, in these valleys, the arts of singing and music have been developed since ancient times. If we look at the big singing schools, Kokan, Beshariq, Margilan-Yozyovon, Andijan, and Baliqchi schools can be a clear proof. Among them, Kuva-Asaka provinces, located between Andijan and Margilon, are known for producing many artists and producing many artists. For example, if we take Kuva Province, famous artists such as Davronboy Hafiz Usta Juma, famous artists of Fergana Province have lived here since ancient times. artists have matured. People's Artist of Uzbekistan Abduhoshim Ismailov, or Tavakkal Kadirov, People's Artist of Uzbekistan, and later, the late People's Chief of Uzbekistan Makhmudjon Tojiboyev, who were inspired by them.

Hafiz, whom we are going to write today, grew up in the village of «Bolalik Qairaghoch» in Kuva province, he was known to our people and worked in the ensemble of status named after Yunus Rajabi for several years and has been teaching young people at the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan. Professor, People's Court of Uzbekistan, recipient of the Order of Selfless Services, unique singer and master artist Makhmudjon Tojiboyev.

Makhmudjon Tojiboyev's entry into art was passed down from his grandfather. That is, Hafiz's grandfather Davronboy Karimov was popularly known as Davronboy Hafiz in Kuva and Fergana. This person was also the teacher of Tavakkal Kadyrov. It was prepared by many students. Although they were engaged in another profession, farming, the hafiz was inherited from their father. Because that person was called Karim Qori by their fathers. Your remembers some of the old people who were blind and had poor eyesight, and they also performed epics by playing the dutor. On the other hand, Davronboy Hafiz, accompanied by a tanbur, was recognized as having gained fame at public gatherings and festivals by singing the Ferghana-Tashkent maqams Bayots, Dugohs, Chorgohs, Shakhnozu Gulyars and many other classic songs of the Ferghana Valley. Now, the songs "Girya and Beksultan" performed by Davronboy Karimov, written by the folklore expedition, are stored in the State Institute of Oriental Studies.

In addition, according to that person, mature hafiz and musicians lived in the area. Egamberdi Mamatov, a well-known hafiz of his time, gave Makhmudjon Tojiboyev his initial education. Egamberdi Mamatov Makhmudjon's grandfathers were students of Davronboy Karimov. This person was an artist who was able to perform some maqams accompanied by a violin in the Ferghana-Tashkent method, from Shashmaqom, which has become a classic in the Ferghana Valley. Unfortunately, not a single magnetic recording or other memorabilia was preserved from that person. But in one or two places, it is known that many big art schools have given him high marks after listening to the songs he sang at local gatherings and weddings. Makhmudjon Tojiboyev first became interested in art when he heard that person's songs when he was still a young child. On the other hand, every person is definitely gifted by the Creator. Without natural talent, it is difficult to achieve any result. We think that Mahmudjon Tojiboyev was also a naturally gifted, thoughtful person who enjoyed the factors of thinking. That's why they found their way in life and achieved a certain status because they were given the ability to perceive statuses and seek to know their secrets.

Mahmudjon Tojiboyev remembers that when he heard Jorakhan Sultanov, Mamurjon Uzokov, Komiljon Otaniyozov and Arifkhan Khotamov on the radio, he fell in love with their mysterious songs. Later, after graduating from high school, he entered the Tashkent Technical College of Cultural Education, where he studied the history and theory of music, and received information on the specialty of rubab from national songs. He studied at this school in the class of

teacher Bahadir Ziyamuhammedov. At one of the meetings, the union invited Dr. Fayzulla Karamatov, Professor of Art Studies, Makhmudjon, to study at the conservatory. At that time, only a student who had completed the music school could pass the exam to the Conservatory. However, the documents of Makhmudjon Tojiboyev, who graduated from the cultural and educational technical school with the recommendation of Fayzulla Muzaffarovich, will be accepted at the Conservatory.

After passing the entrance exams with excellent grades, you will be admitted to the ranks of students.

At the Dargah of Knowledge, young Makhmudjon takes lessons from the late teachers Arif Ota Alimakhsumov, Fattakhan Mamadaliyev, and Turgun Almatov from the tanbur. Among them, such teachers as Makhmudjon Muhammedov Shavkat Mirzayev, Hamidjon Jalolov worked in the department of traditional performance at that time, and Makhmudjon enjoyed the knowledge and practical training of these teachers. Makhmudjon Tojiboyev, who was educated by such teachers and later studied in the 4th year of the Conservatory, was invited by his teacher Arif Ota Alimakhsumov to a temporary job in the makomchilar ensemble. This is how Makhmudjon's entry into the master ensemble, the elite ensemble of his time, begins.

Makhmudjon begins to master the secrets of maqam performance while standing in the ranks of the dargahs of his time. Even after finishing his studies at the conservatory, he continues his work in the Yunus Rajabi makom ensemble under the Uzbekistan Television and Radio Company. This dargah serves as a huge laboratory for Makhmudjon to study the performance and science of the art of status.

Makhmudjon, who has a deep mind, sharp thinking, and thirst for knowledge, tries to master the science of status in every way. He tries to understand the main elements of the most advanced Hafiz performance schools of his time and scientifically integrate them into his performance practice. He has been working creatively and practically at this school for almost 17 years together with his mentors. Together with the team, he actively participates in writing more than 100 status samples, works of composers and samples of folk songs to the radio's golden fund.

Since 2000, he has been teaching at the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan. In fact, the period when Makhmudjon Tojiboyev worked in the team of makomchilar ensemble named after Yunus Rajabi should be considered as a special creative period. Because the period in which Makhmudjon Tojiboyev was

formed as an artist, a hafiz and a skilled musician is mainly related to his work in the Makam ensemble. Here, he had the privilege of working with a number of famous teachers such as Arif Alimaksumov, Ochilkhan Otakhanov, Eson Lutfullayev, Arifkhan Hotamov, Berta Davidova, Komuna Ismoilova, Hadiya Yusupova, and achieved performance perfection in this ensemble. People's Artist of Uzbekistan, winner of the «Order of Respect for the Country» Abduhoshim Ismailov, who was the leader of the makomchilar ensemble, was also of special importance in the work of Makhmudjon Tojiboyev. The reason is that Makhmudjon took part in recording the status on the first gramophone record after receiving training from a teacher who started work with a new perspective and a new perspective.

At that time, with Mahmudjon Yoldoshev, who was accepted into the maqam ensemble, the two Makhmudjons managed to turn the ensemble into a good hafiz. In many cases, Abduhoshim Ismailov entrusted the most important positions of reliable parties to the middle parties and taught them to be the leader himself. These actions of the teacher showed their results. At that time, the statuses of “Buzruk”, “Rost”, “Navo”, “Dugoh”, “Segoh”, “Iroq” were almost completely rewritten in the golden fund of the radio and were recognized in the first international competitions of gramophone records.

During 1998-2000, Professor Fattakhkan Mamadaliyev, People's Office of Uzbekistan, was teaching students in traditional performance at the Conservatory. At that time, Fattakhkan Mamadaliyev's health deteriorated. In the last days of Fattakhkan Mamadaliyev's life, Mahmudjon Tojiboyev visited him frequently and informed him about his condition. One day, the teacher asked Mahmudjon to go to the Conservatory to continue his work, and Mahmudjon Tojiboyev accepted his request, and from that day he began to work with Fattakhkan Mamadaliyev's students to implement the teacher's instructions. Now, when he consulted with his teacher Ochilkhan Otakhanov about moving directly from the radio to the Conservatory, Ochilkhan Otakhanov also supported this proposal. Since 2000, Mahmudjon Tojiboyev finished his career in the ensemble of makomists and started his career in the traditional singing department of the Conservatory.

In Makhmudjon Tojiboyev's career in the art of status art, master artist Ochilkhan Otakhanov had a great influence and place. The reason is that Ochilkhan Otakhanov is an artist who has left a unique mark in the performance of Uzbek status and has earned his place. In addition, the school of performance, culture, science, and interpretation philosophy of the teacher captivated

Makhmudjon. And most importantly, Makhmudjon worked together with this person until the end of his life in creative, practical, teacher-student and humanitarian relations.

Makhmudjon was honored to walk together with his teacher in public service and in crowds for almost 16 years. At this point, one more thing should be noted that an artist cannot reach high levels by acquiring only performance skills. In this place, the artist's spiritual world, his inner world, his spiritual experiences are also very important.

In his words, Makhmudjon Tojiboyev often emphasized that he learned from his teacher Ochilkhan Otakhanov not only how to sing, but also the rules of ethics necessary for an artist, how an artist should behave in public. has emphasized many times that it should be kept. Walking together with Ochilkhan Otakhanov, Makhmudjon Tojiboyev has emphasized that he learned a lot of science in terms of art ethics, manners, spiritual and moral image. It is necessary to mention this, especially in mentor-discipleship, it is necessary to emphasize a lot about the role of the mentor in raising the disciple's spirituality, bringing him to maturity spiritually and intellectually. Because the times demand it.

When Makhmudjon Tojiboyev came to the Conservatory to work in the department of traditional performance, there was a time when Rifatulla Kasimov managed the department very skillfully. Rifatulla Kasimov was one of the real teachers who had a place in our national performance and fully mastered the basics of traditional performance pedagogy. Even now, experts in the field admit it with words. One of the achievements of Professor Rifatulla Kasimov was that he attracted qualified and talented specialists to the Conservatory and created a unique spiritual atmosphere in the department. For example, People's Artist of Uzbekistan «Order of Merit» Turgun Ota Alimatov, People's Court of Uzbekistan Kuvondik Iskandarov, Professor Matnazar Khudoynazarov, People's Artist of Uzbekistan Zamira Suyunova, Honored Artist of Uzbekistan Komila Bo He used their experience by attracting famous artists in the field of pedagogy.

M. Tojiboyev, who worked effectively for many years and managed to train hundreds of students, since 2017, together with his work at the conservatory, he has also been working as the head of the department of the newly established Uzbek National Status Art Center «Master-Apprentice School». was able to make a great contribution to the reformation of the industry and its development on the scale of our republic, especially in the creation of exemplary makom ensembles in all regions, in the creation of scientific developments, and most importantly, in the development of a new generation in the culture of makom

art. He created the textbook «Maqom alifbosi» for the education of the young generation. Only «Maqom saboqlari» left a worthy legacy for the next generation with electronic lectures, that is, more than 60 master classes.

Makhmudjon Tojiboyev had a high intellectual capacity, a scholar of worldly and religious sciences, a philosopher of our time. It is a fact that these were manifested in his lectures, especially in his musical and singing performances. The creative legacy of Makhmudjon Tojiboyev is endless. Learning it and leaving it as a program to younger generations is relevant for the educational process of our time. The mastery of the secrets of performance of status is definitely achieved in harmony with scientific aspects. For this, the scientific and practical legacy of Makhmudjon Tojiboyev is an important factor. The great artist of our country, distinguished scientist, professor Makhmudjon Tojiboyev left this mortal world on July 11, 2020. However, there is no doubt that the scientific and practical legacy left by Hafiz will serve the development of the art of status, the study of the science of status, for researchers and students for many years.

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